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541 Khmu

Source:

Svantesson, Jan-Olof (1983). Kammu phonology and morphology

Lund: CWK Gleerup

Travaux de l'Institut de Linguistique de Lund ; 18

PL 4351 SVA 1983

(description of the Yùan dialect as spoken in the Ban Mo region, but it could be extended to account for the Yuan dialect in general and (with minor adjustments) for other Northern dialects)

--> main source for information, exceptions are mentioned

Premrirat, Suwilai (1987). Khmu, a minority language of Thailand

Canberra: Australian National Univ.

Papers in South-East Asian linguistics ; 10

Pacific Linguistics : Series A, Occasional Papers ; 75

PL 3501 PAP-10

(description of the dialect spoken by the Khmu of Barn Huay Yen, in Barn Muangkarn village, Chiengkong district of Chiengrai province, Thailand)

Premrirat, Suwilai (2001). "Tonogenesis in Khmu dialects of SEA."

in: Mon-Khmer Studies: a Journal of Southeast Asian Linguistics and Languages 31: 47-56.

Premrirat, Suwilai (2004). "Register complex and tonogenesis in Khmu dialects."

Mon-Khmer Studies: A Journal of Southeast Asian Linguistics and Languages 34: 1-17.

I. Language Profile

A language of [Laos](#)

ISO/DIS 639-3: [kjj](#)

Population: 389,694 in Laos (1985 F. Proschan). Population total all countries: 479,739.

Region: Scattered through northern Laos. Also spoken in China, France, Myanmar, Thailand, USA, Viet Nam.

Alternate names: Kmhmu, Khmu', Khamu, Kamu, Kammu, Khamuk, Kamhmu, Khomu, Mou, Pouteng, Pu Thenh, Tenh, Theng, Lao Terng

Dialects: Yuan, Khroong (Krong), Luang Prabang, Sayabury, Lyy, Rok, U, Hat.

Classification: [Austro-Asiatic](#), [Mon-Khmer](#), [Northern Mon-Khmer](#), [Khmuic](#), [Mal-Khmu'](#), [Khmu'](#)

Language development: Duota script in China. Bible portions: 1918.

Comments: SVO. Traditional religion.

Also spoken in:

[China](#)

Language name: Khmu

Population: 1,600 in China (1990).

Region: Mengla and Jinghong counties of Xishuangbanna Prefecture, southwestern Yunnan.

Alternate names: Kammu, Khamu, Khmu', Khamuk, Kamhmu, Kamu, Kemu, Khomu, Mou, Lao Terng, Pouteng, Theng

Comments: Khmu was counted separately in the 1982 census and combined into a group of 'Undetermined Minorities'. It may soon be recognized as an official nationality. Phsing (Bit) is regarded as Khmu in China, but is in the Palaungic branch (Svantesson 1990).

[Myanmar](#)

Language name: Khmu

Alternate names: Kmhm, Khmu', Kamu, Kammu, Khamuk, Kamhmu, Khomu, Mou, Pouteng, Pu Thenh, Tenh, Theng, Lao Terng

[Thailand](#)

Language name: Khmu

Population: 31,403 in Thailand (2000 WCD).

Region: Scattered through Thailand, Chiangrai, Nan, Phayao.

Alternate names: Kmhm, Khamu, Khmu', Khamuk, Kamhmu, Kamu, Kha Khmu, Kammu, Tmooy, Mou, Luu, Pouteng

Comments: Traditional religion, Christian.

[Viet Nam](#)

Language name: Khmu

Population: 56,542 in Viet Nam (1999 census).

Region: Son La, Lai Chau, Nghe An, and Yen Bai provinces.

Alternate names: Kmhm, Khomu, Khamu, Mun Xen, Xa Cau, Kha Cau, Cam Mu

Comments: Traditional religion, Christian.

II. Morpheme Types

- no inflectional morphology for nouns (number, gender, case)
- no inflectional morphology for verbs (tense, aspect, mood, clitic pronouns)
- affixation and reduplication only in derivational processes

i. root

ii. preposed restricted formative

- often realized as minor syllables
- NMLZ (V): rn- carries low tone, attaches only to monosyllabic roots, forming a sesqisyllabic unit without changing the tone of the main syllable
- CAUS (V) p-, pn- (allomorph operating on monosyllabic words)
ex. há:n 'to die' > phá:n 'to kill'
sís 'to sleep' > p̀̀sís 'to put to sleep'
- Resultative (V) hn-
ex. cá:k 'to tear' > h́cá:k 'torn'
- Reciprocal (V)

iii. Preposed unrestricted formative

- sole one: verb-forming prefix kn- (V)
- operates on words from different word-classes
- basic meaning of the derived word is 'to say ...'
ex. k̀̀kúr 'to call chickens' < kúr kúr 'call for chickens'

iv. Interposed restricted formative

- NMLZ (V): usually operates on monosyllabic words forming a sesqisyllabic one
onset of the major syllable becomes the onset of the minor syllable in the derived form
ex. k̀̀há:c 'shovel' < khá:c 'to shovel' (here the nominalizing affix /-rn-/ has the allomorph -r- which appears if the root begins with a cluster)
h́rnò:m 'bamboo strip (instr.); bundle (factitive)' (from hó:m 'to tie')
- CAUS -m- (V) (allomorph operating on sesqisyllabic words with non-tonal minor syllables)
- inserted after the first segment of the root --> derived word is sesqisyllabic with /m/ as minor syllable coda

iv. Particle

- verb negation pé: preceding the verb
- NMLZ particle śn̄:
 - combines with units larger than words (verb-phrases and clauses) and nominalizes them
 - ex. śn̄ ʔò? klám 'that which I carry'
NMLZ 1.sg carry
 - occurs as prefix s̄n̄- (minor syllable with high tone) when attached to a monosyllabic word, forming a sesqisyllabic unit without changing the tone of

the main syllable

ex. s'jyiaŋ 'black thing; opium' < yiaŋ 'black'

III. Word

- consists of one or more „word-bases” (phonological units)
- word-base: a V (short, long or diphthong) followed by one or zero consonants and preceded by one or more consonants (one of which may be syllabic): monosyllabic or sesquisyllabic unit
- phonological rules apply within a word-base
- most words consists of one word-base
- most multi-based words are formed by reduplication
- ex. c'iaŋ 'foot'
s'icru:s'icri: '(expressive) silence'

word base	-- minor syllable	- onset	
		- (coda)	
	-- major syllable	- onset	
		- rhyme	- peak (vowel)
			- coda

(elements in parentheses are optional)

minor and major syllable can be combined almost freely, few restrictions (see Syllable chapter)

Premrirat, Suwilai (1987):

- a phonological word may be defined as a unit having one main (stressed) syllable, may be preceded by one unstressed, rarely two unstressed syllables

IV. Syllable Structure

Premrirat, Suwilai (2004):

- syllable structure interacts with prosodic features (see tone section) --> dialectal differences according to differences in the prosodic structure
- in the eastern dialect group both initial and final consonants in the minor syllable are preserved, whereas western dialects that developed a register contrast, the presyllable becomes syllabic and the western dialects that developed a tone contrast the entire presyllable or the initial consonant of the presyllable is deleted; however there are some western dialects (e.g. Yuan, the variety described by Svantesson 1983) that have developed a tone contrast but still keep presyllable (sesquisyllabic)
- eastern dialects represent the conservative stage

Svantesson (1983)

3 syllable types: major syllables, tonal minor syllable, non-tonal minor syllables

major syllable:

- has tone
- syllabic element: V
- one cooccurrence restriction between onset and coda: *rVr

onset:

- all consonant phonemes can be found + clusters /pl, pr, tr, cr, kl, kr, kw, k^hw/

(Premsrirat, Suwilai (1987) adds cluster of aspirated stop+trill for the variety he describes)

- restrictions on the cooccurrence of onset consonants and tones:
--> with both tones: voiceless stops /p, t, c, k/; nasals /m, n, ɲ, ŋ/; liquids /l, r/; glides /w, y/
--> with low tone: /ʔ/
--> with high tone: /p^h, t^h, c^h, k^h/(BUT: the status of the aspirated voiceless stops is somewhat debatable - Premsrirat, Suwilai (1987) argues for a sequence of stop+h because an infix can split them up); implosive, voiced stops /b, d/; voiceless fricatives /s, h/; laryngealized glides /w̥, y̥/

- exceptions from these rules are found in some recent Lao loans, interjections, particles
- when there is an onset cluster, the first C influences the tone

rhyme: *aspirated stops, *implosives, *laryngealized glides

- stops are unreleased
- /h/ is realized as [x]
- /ʔ/ occurs only after short vowels and diphthongs
- the coda consonant position is zero when the nucleus is filled by a long V or a diphthong (but not every long vowel and diphthong is followed by an empty coda slot)
- /ɛ/, /ɔ/ combine only with the codas /h/, /ʔ/
- /h/ does not appear after long vowels and the non-low front vowels /i, e/
- back rounded vowels do not combine with the coda /w/
- front vowels do not combine with coda /y/

Minor syllable:

- unstressed
- consists of a consonant onset and a coda
- coda as syllabic element is either a sonorant consonant or non-sonorant consonant (only in assimilated forms) or zero – in the last two cases the syllabicity is carried by a schwa, at least in careful speech
- ex. /clò:ŋ/ [cə'lò:ŋ] 'boat'
- minor syllables with codas other than zero have tone, but the minor syllable tone seldom serves to distinguish between different words

- certain minor syllables are combinatorilly free, i.e. they can be combined with any major syllable, others are subject to the following restrictions:
 - either the the codas of the major and minor syllables must be identical, or the place of articulation of the (nasal) coda of the minor syllable must be the same as that of the initial (stop) consonant of the major syllable
 - a liquid as minor syllable coda cannot be followed by a liquid as major syllable onset, except that the sequence rl occurs in several examples
- the only codas in minor syllables (except for zero codas) which are combinatorilly free are /m, n, ŋ, l/
- minor syllables with codas /p, t, c, k, ɲ, s, w, y/ are always “coda-assimilated”, i.e. their coda is identical to the coda of the major syllable of the same word-base – most words with such minor syllables are either prefixed forms or coda-infixed expressives, but assimilation of prefixes is not always obligatory
- ex. NMLZ rn-: r̀nhó:m ~ r̀nhó:m 'tying' from hó:m 'to tie'
- there seem to be restrictions against onset and codas having the same place of articulation, although this is not a strict rule, thus *pp, *pm, *pw, *cc, *cɲ, *cs, *cy do not occur, and kɲ is found only as a coda-assimilated form
- many of the minor syllables occur only in expressives and reduplicatives
- in careful and slow speech there can be transitional vowels which are fully predictable from the environment

- 2 types due to tone:
 - > tonal: do not influence the tone of the major syllable
 - > non-tonal:
 - does not have tone of their own, but may influence the tone of the major syllable
 - common: p, t, c, k, s, h as onset and zero codas

- a word-base consists of one major syllable which can be preceded by one minor syllable --> sesquisyllabic
- the term “polysyllabic” is reserved for word-bases consisting of more than one major syllables
- ex.

ɲàr	'cold' (monosyllabic)
k̀r̀ǹǹh	'cutting board' (sesquisyllabic)
pcú:r	'to lower' (sesquisyllabic, minor syllable is non-tonal)

- syllabification rule: a syllable boundary is inserted as far to the left as possible, leaving a single consonant or a cluster between it and the vowel

- allomorphy due to phonotactics: prefix for monosyllabics, infix for sesquisyllabic words
 - ex. causative pn- ~ -m-
- klé? 'to appear' p̀ǹklé? 'to show' (prefix forms its own tone-group)

tlú:y 'to hang (intr.) trnú:y 'to hang (tr.)'

V. _____ Tone

Premrirat, Suwilai (2004)

- prosodic situation in Khmu may be best described as « register complex » because it consists of phonetic features and their relationships: consonant voicing, voice quality (phonation), aspiration, pitch level, contour etc.
 - different dialects select different phonetic features to highlight their prominent prosodic characteristics
 - Eastern dialect group: no tone, no register, but have a consonant voicing distinction in the initial consonants
 - Western dialects: some have a lax-tense register contrast, whereas others have tonal contrast
- > three types:
- 1) voice quality contrast
 - 2) tone contrast and aspirated initial stop consonant
 - 3) tone contrast
- if there is tone contrast, then low vs. high
 - high tone has two variants: high and rising-falling

The following description is based on the Yuan dialect (belongs to the western group) described in Svantesson (1987)

- two tones: high and low
- phonetically the tone manifests itself on the voiced part of a syllable
- each vowel has either high or low tone, other segments have tone if they are sonority peaks, i.e. if they are sonorants and followed by a non-tonal segment
- if there is a tonal consonant, it becomes the coda of a minor syllable
- word-bases which are not assigned any tonal consonant surface monosyllabic or sesquisyllabic with zero coda
- a word-base has as many tone-groups as it has tones, tone-group boundaries coincide with syllable boundaries

Tone Assignment Rule:

Tone is determined by the tone-group initial consonant :

- high tone is assigned to /b/, /d/, /w/, /y/, /p/, /t/, /c/, /k/, /s/, /h/
- low tone is assigned to /b/, /d/, /j/, /g/ (all these underlyingly voiced segments surface as their voiceless counterparts), /m/, /n/, /ŋ/, /l/, /r/, /y/, /w/, /
?/

Tone sandhi rule (dissimilation): A high tone in a minor syllable becomes low if the major syllable tone is high and if the minor syllable onset is underlyingly an unaspirated stop.

Tonal morphophonology:

- obstruent prefixes:

when a prefix consisting of an obstruent attaches to a root, the prefixed word either remains monosyllabic or becomes sesquisyllabic with a minor non-tonal syllable, therefore the obstruent prefix is tone-group initial and determines the tone of the prefixed word according to the tone assignment rule

ex. lian 'to come out' > plían 'to take out'

- Infixes:

If an infix consists of only one segment and is infixed into a word with a single initial consonant, the derived word consists of only one tone group and the tone is not changed – this occurs only with the nominalizing infix.

In other instances, the first element of the infix becomes a (tonal) minor syllable coda, the major syllable tone is then determined by the second element of the infix, if there is one, otherwise by the second segment of the root (since this segment becomes tone group initial).

ex. pá:t 'to saw' pǎnà:t 'saw'

VI. Phonological Processes

i. Stop Epenthesis

- in words with nasal coda minor syllable and liquid major syllable initial, a homorganic stop is often inserted after the nasal if it can form a major syllable onset cluster with the liquid.
- The tone of the major syllable remains low.
- In some instances the forms with or without epenthetic stop are in free variation, in other instances the epenthesis is obligatorily.
- Stop insertion seems to be impossible if the major syllable has high tone
- epenthesis has not been found in words with /ŋr/ or the palatal nasal
- stops cannot be inserted in words with /nl/, since /dl/ is not a possible major syllable onset

ii. "Wandering" Palatality

- when the nominalizing infix /-rn-/ is inserted into words with onset /c/, /c/ becomes [t] and /n/ becomes [ɲ]

ex. cák 'to pick' > tǎnàk 'toothpick'

ii. Nasal Assimilation

- a nasal minor syllable coda is sometimes assimilated to the place of articulation of a following stop
- does not take place in all words

ex. pùh 'to carry in a strap' > rǎpùh 'burden'

VII. Stress

Premrsirat, Suwilai (1987)

- one main stress per word
- the major syllable which is always the last gets the main stress

VIII. Reduplication

- repetition of the word base with or without change of some part of it
 - used with a general intensifying meaning or as regular word-forming device in expressives
 - reduplication without changes, ex. tàl tàl 'kind of cicada'
 - onset-changing reduplication, ex. ʔà:m plá:m 'butterfly'
 - peak-changing reduplication, ex. sú:t sí:t 'to rub against'
 - coda-changing reduplication, ex. ʔò:r ʔò:k 'water-rail (bird)'
 - rhyme-changing reduplication, ex. pó:l páŋ 'to roll'
 - in sesquisyllabic words the minor syllable is repeated without change except in coda-assimilated minor syllables
 - double reduplication: each word base is reduplicated separately, and both the reduplicated forms are put after the original forms
- ex. kítù:t tì:t kítùŋ tàŋ, from kítù:t tì:t '(expressive) search desperately'

IX. Lao Loan Word

- Tai words with original voiced (non-implosive) stops have an aspirated unvoiced stop in modern Lao
- > in Kammu they often have two variant pronunciation: with aspirated or unaspirated voiceless stop, and with low tone in both cases (aspirated stop onsets are not otherwise combined with low tone)
- Lao tones have left no trace
 - usually monosyllabic
 - Lao loans in Khmu can have only the (major syllable) codas /p, t, k, m, n, ŋ, w, y, ʔ/ and zero coda